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The Review of the African Union's Environmental Year. The Progressive Development of Environmental Law

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(1) Introduction

The activity of the African Union at the time of Covid-19 is not as important as in past years. However, it is important to point out that the main organs of the African continental organization, notably the Assembly and the Executive Council, were able to meet in ordinary and extraordinary sessions. In this regard, the Assembly held its Thirty-third Ordinary Session in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, on 9 and 10 February 2020, and the Executive Council held its Thirty-sixth Ordinary Session on 6 and 7 February 2020. This year, the agendas of the two bodies included various aspects relating to the environment. Our report will first present the decisions and statements of the Assembly before outlining those of the Executive Council.

(2) The Assembly of the African Union

The Assembly held its Thirty-third Ordinary Session in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, on 9 and 10 February 2020. During this session, the Assembly discussed several issues including climate change, cultural heritage, refugees, returnees and displaced persons.

(A) Climate Change

Through its decision Assembly/AU/Dec.764(XXXIII), the Assembly welcomed the report of the African Heads of State and Government Committee on Climate Change (CAHOSCC), presented by its Coordinator Cyril RAMAPHOSA, President of the Republic of South Africa. The CAHOSCC report reflected the outcomes of the 25th

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Conference of the Parties (COP 25) to the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), the 15th Meeting of the Parties serving as the Conference of the Parties to its Kyoto Protocol (CMP 15) and the second session of the Conference of the Parties serving as the Meeting of the Parties to the Paris Agreement (MCP 2).

On the same occasion, the African Ministerial Conference on the Environment (AMCEN) and the meetings of the African Group of Negotiators (AGN), notably the Durban and Madrid meetings, reported on the progress of preparations for the forthcoming COPs.

The decision underscored the CAHOSCC's effort to federate Africa's voice in international climate negotiations through a common political orientation in line with the spirit of pan-Africanism. In this regard, it welcomed the institutional support provided by the African Union Commission (AUC) and all relevant partners, in particular the African Development Bank (AfDB), United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the Republic of Germany. Also, the decision acknowledged the endeavour of the Congo Basin Climate Commission (CCBC) and the Sahel Climate Commission on the Adaptation Initiative and the African Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI) and applauded the successful launch of the Climate Commission for African Island States by the Republic of Seychelles.

In order to foster synergies between those initiatives and to stave off fragmented efforts, the Assembly found it a straightforward choice to make that the Chairs of the Climate Commission for the Sahel Region, the Chair of the Climate Commission for African Island States, the Chair of the African Adaptation Initiative, and the Chair of the African Renewable Energy Initiative should join the CAHOSCC.

The Assembly welcomed and endorsed the international scientific consensus on climate change that recently emerged from the three reports of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), including the 1.5 degree Global Warming Report, the Report on Climate Change and Land, the Report on Oceans and Cryosphere in a Changing Climate. Moreover, it emphasised the necessity for ambitious action and impact to address climate change in Africa.

However, the Assembly expressed concern about the increase in global emissions and the failure of major emitting countries to meet their commitments. Furthermore, the decision reiterated the willingness of African Union States to implement their international climate commitments in conjunction with social issues such as poverty eradication, and so. Then, the decision referred to the increasing vulnerability of the African continent to the recent impacts of climate change with its economic and non-economic consequences. In this regard, it set out the following brief statement in paragraph 12:

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(...) The African continent as a whole is facing unprecedented pressure owing to various extreme weather events and slow-onset events accentuated by climate change, including flash floods; heavy rainfall, water scarcity and drought, which has displaced thousands of people and caused deaths in North Africa; landslides, which have caused thousands of deaths in Central Africa; severe drought, affecting livestock, water, crops, wildlife and the energy sector in East Africa; extreme events in the Western Africa region, which have caused flash floods, resulting in the loss of lives, displacing thousands and destroying infrastructure; and cyclones and drought, which have caused the deaths of thousands and destroyed homes and properties in southern Africa, and express solidarity with countries and people that have been impacted by climate related disasters around the world.

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The African Union's commitment to respect the international climate was reiterated as essential for the effective implementation of the 2015 Paris Agreement, and the Assembly sustained that such an effort will only be successful down the road if developed countries continue to meet their international commitments under the Kyoto Protocol.

Given that the implementation of the Paris agreement will begin in 2021, the Assembly was satisfied with the commitments made to replenish the Green Climate Fund (GCF) and its contribution to reducing emission rates. It then called on developed countries to provide additional funds to the Adaptation Fund, the Global Environment Facility and the Green Climate Fund.

Pursuant to Article 3 of the Paris Agreement, the Assembly advocated a revision and strengthening Nationally Determined Contributions (NDC) of African States in 2020. It invited them to combine information on mitigation, adaptation and the implementation of the Paris Agreement. It also reminded African countries of the urgency of adaptation and the inclusion in adaptation mechanisms of social concerns such as the eradication of hunger as well as the need to plan for such adaptation. Finally, it invited African States to report on their adaptation needs, gaps, planning, efforts and actions in order to raise the ambition of mitigation and adaptation measures through the market-based mechanisms of the Paris Agreement.

Furthermore, the decision drew the attention of the Member States to the need to reconcile the fight against climate change with African trade initiatives and the challenges of the African continental free trade agreement. In this sense, the fight against climate change should not per se be an obstacle to African countries' exports.

In short, the Assembly reiterated its interest in federating Africa's single voice and coordinating its climate action while it expressed satisfaction with the work initiated by the Africa Adaptation Initiative (AAI), the African Renewable Energy Initiative (AREI), the Initiative for the Adaptation of African Agriculture to Climate Change (AAA Initiative) and the climate commissions of Africa, notably the Climate Commission for the Congo Basin, the Climate Commission for the Sahel Region and the Climate Commission for the African Island States. In addition, it supported Decision 28 of the 2019 session of CAHOSCC which called on the commission to organise an African summit on climate change in 2020 before COP26.

(B) African natural and cultural heritage

On the heels of the debate on the African cultural heritage, the Thirty-third Ordinary Session of the Assembly led to the adoption of the decision Doc. Assembly/AU/17(XXXIII) on Arts, culture and heritage. In the first place, the Assembly welcomed the report prepared by the Leader of the African Union for the Promotion, Popularisation and Enhancement of Arts, Culture and Heritage on the Continent one year after his appointment by the African Heads of State and Government. One of the proposals contained in the said report aimed at setting up a Peer Council on Arts, Culture and Heritage, whose mission would be to define the main strategic orientations of the African Union applicable in this field and to give the necessary impetus to the activities of the latter.

Then, the Assembly asserted the central role of culture, arts and heritage in the implementation of Agenda 2063. For that reason, it urged Member States to complete the ratification process of the African Charter for Cultural Renaissance already initiated by fourteen other States. Similarly, it brought the attention of Member States to the lack of budgetary allocations in this area and urged them to make sure that at least 1% of their national budgets are allocated from 2030 onwards.

Towards this end, the Assembly approved a proposal brought up to its attention by the report designed by the leader-designate in this area concerning the declaration of the year 2021 as the year of the African Union for the Arts, Culture and Heritage. To this effect, it requested the latter to submit a mid-term report at the Thirty-fourth ordinary session of the Assembly.

Furthermore, it is worth noting that the Assembly subsumed the issue of arts and culture within the framework of the ongoing institutional reform process of the African Union and invited partnerships between States and the private sector to support the work of the African World Heritage Fund (AWHF).

Finally, as African heritage represents an asset for the continent, the Assembly demanded that the AWHF work on a sustainable financing mechanism to protect African heritage of outstanding value.

(C) Refugees, Returnees and Displaced Persons in Africa

In addition to decisions of its Thirty-third Ordinary Session, the Assembly adopted a Declaration Assembly/AU/Decl.1(XXXIII) on the 2019 Theme on Refugees, Returnees and Displaced Persons in Africa: Towards a Durable Solution to Forced Displacement in Africa. The Declaration is an important political instrument through which the Assembly encouraged Member States that have hosted refugees and internally displaced persons (IDPs) to use African solutions, in line with the spirit of Pan-Africanism, when it comes to various humanitarian crises facing the African continent. In this regard, the Assembly concentrated on the urgency to address the causes of forced displacement in Africa and encouraged Member States to work out sustainable solutions and adapted to the African context. Through the legal and political instruments currently in force within the African Union, it is important to strengthen humanitarian interventions with the support of international partners.

The declaration stated that Member States should not limit themselves to emergency response, but should double their efforts in humanitarian response well before emergencies occur. Prevention is necessary for a variety of reasons, including the current context in Africa which is characterised by a proliferation of humanitarian problems resulting from various political situations, namely conflict, terrorism, political instability, natural disasters, environmental degradation and climate change. As a result, Member States need to identify and address the structural and root causes that lead to the different forms of displacement in Africa. Consequently, the Assembly urged Member States to establish an early warning system in order to make the response rapid and effective.

With a view to mobilizing African States to address the problem of refugees and displaced persons in Africa, particularly with regard to specific protracted situations of forced displacement, the Assembly accentuated the need for a clear will of Heads of State to be expressed and for an effective political effort to be made. To this end, it reiterated its determination to address the problem of refugees and IDPs in an inclusive manner with other forms of phenomena that constitute challenges for the continent.

In this regard, the Assembly indicated that the problem as it relates to refugees and displaced persons cannot be fully resolved if it is treated as an isolated issue. It should be integrated into efforts aimed at activities under the theme for the year 2020: 'Silencing guns: Creating an enabling environment for Africa'. Development.'

The Assembly placed a particular emphasis on the role of international partnerships between Member States, Regional Economic Communities (RECs) and the Commission. It therefore welcomed the work undertaken in such a context with regard to the organisation of a High-level Continental Conference on the

Humanitarian Situation in Africa in Malabo, Equatorial Guinea. As a matter of fact, the Assembly recalled that it was imperative—at the stage of these partnerships as well—to foster an inclusive treatment of those issues. Indeed, Member States, RECs and the Commission must ensure that issues related to refugees and IDPs always include governance, peace, post-conflict reconstruction and recovery, development and climate change. It is indeed this overall cohesion that should be found in policies, strategies and mechanisms to address forced displacement. Furthermore, these partnerships cannot exclude key actors who are bearing the brunt of these problems, including affected populations, refugees and IDPs, because durable solutions can only stem from their effective participation.

Thus, partnerships between Member States, the RECs and the Commission must also consider the necessary mobilisation of funding and financial resources that can support both solutions to displacement and humanitarian crises as well as the ongoing emergencies that are being experienced on the African continent. In this regard, the Assembly invited the Commission to consult Member States and to support the Commission in the process of resettlement of IDPs in third countries. That being said, the Commission must now take part in the process and no longer be an external stakeholder to resolving this problem on the ground. Accordingly, the Commission will participate in the coordination and support of displaced persons and refugees in their free and guided choice, under the relevant instruments of international law, between repatriation, local integration and recovery. At the same time, the Assembly urged the immediate lifting of international sanctions against African countries in order to mitigate the adverse effects of humanitarian crises.

In order to prevent disbanded efforts, the Assembly requested the Specialized Technical Committee on Justice and Legal Affairs to finalize the process of drafting the Protocol to the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights on Specific Aspects of the Right to a Nationality and the Elimination of Statelessness in Africa. In this respect, the draft should be submitted to the 34th Ordinary Session of the AU Assembly for consideration and adoption. In addition, the Assembly received with acclamation the ratification of the 2009 AU Convention for the Protection and Assistance of Internally Displaced Persons in Africa by Equatorial Guinea, Somalia and Southern Sudan. Accordingly, it called on the 15 Member States that have not signed the Convention and the 26 others that have not yet ratified it to do so. However, with a view to strengthening the treaty circle of the 1969 OAU Convention Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa—still open for ratification—the Assembly encouraged the remaining 12 Member States to sign it and the 9 that have not ratified it to do so.

At the State level, the Assembly stressed that they should establish 'national infrastructures for peace with a view to ensuring reconciliation, social harmony and cohesion in the nation-building process, addressing the specific needs of vulnerable social groups such as women, children, youth, the disabled and the elderly and

ensuring their full and effective participation.’ As such, they are responsible for developing internal mechanisms to strengthen their national systems for disaster-related displacement, risk and disaster reduction and early warning. As such, they must also ensure that the mechanisms—to be implemented—are consistent with the Sendai Framework, the African Regional Strategy for Disaster Risk Reduction and the Programme of Action for the Implementation of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 in Africa.

As a result, Member States must also ensure that the problem of IDPs is not an isolated or stand-alone issue, but one that is addressed as part of a broader package of measures to mitigate displacement linked to the adverse effects of environmental degradation, extreme weather and climate change.

(D) African Natural and Cultural Heritage Fund

The Assembly expressed first its support for the advocacy for the African World Heritage Fund, organized at the 33rd Assembly of the African Union on 9 February 2020 in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. Then, the Assembly proceeded to declare that: ‘(...) Africa's rich and diverse heritage is an essential asset to make the continent known on the international scene and to build sustainable development, integration and peace in Africa.’ (Para. 1).

In this regard, it invited the African World Heritage Fund to ‘(...) propose a sustainable financing mechanism to protect African heritage of outstanding value and to organize a fundraising event in 2021 under the leadership of the African Union Champion for Arts, Culture and Heritage and in collaboration with the African Union.’ In order to give meaning to the work of the African World Heritage Fund for the characterization, protection and promotion of African natural and cultural heritage, the Assembly encouraged partnerships between Member States and private actors.

(3) The Executive Council

The Thirty-six Ordinary Session of the Executive Council was held on 6 and 7 February 2020, in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia. During the session, the Executive Council discussed mainly a couple of issues relating to environment.

(A) Migration, Refugees and Displaced Persons in Africa

In its decision EX.CL/Dec.1074(XXXVI), the Executive Council acknowledged the report of the Third Ordinary Session of the CTS on Migration, Refugees and Displaced Persons in Africa, held from 7 to 8 November 2019 in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, under the theme of the year: ‘Refugees, Returnees and Internally Displaced Persons: Towards Durable Solutions to Forced Displacement in Africa.’ In addition, it invited Member States to ratify and implement the 1969 OAU Convention

Governing the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa and the 2009 AU Convention on the Protection and Assistance to Internally Displaced Persons in Africa.

With a view to strengthening the mechanisms for managing the daunting problem of displacement in Africa, the Executive Council welcomed the efforts being made towards the establishment of specialized technical offices, including the establishment and operationalization of the African Centre for Migration Studies and Research, the African Migration Observatory and the Continental Operational Centre in Khartoum. Similarly, it urged various departments to develop synergies in their work on the implementation of the 2020 theme ‘Silencing the guns: creating an enabling environment for socio-economic development.’ To this end, the Department of Political Affairs was invited to work with the Peace and Security Department to highlight the inter-relationships that stem from forced displacement and conflict situations.

On the recommendations of the STC on Migration, Refugees and Displaced Persons in Africa, the Executive Council was also invited to designate a leader to spearhead the campaign for the ratification of the Protocol to the Treaty establishing the African Economic Community on the Free Movement of Persons, the Right of Residence and the Right of Establishment in Member States.

Moreover, the Executive Council recognized the imperative need to start the activities of the African Humanitarian Agency in order to adapt the African response to the various humanitarian challenges. Thereupon, it instructed the Commission to move forward with the process of approving the feasibility study of the said Agency, including the preparation of a draft statute including the proposed administrative structure and budgetary evaluation. Through this process, the Commission should ensure the participation of States and RECs. In addition, the Executive Council adopted ‘the Terms of Reference of the Pan-African Forum on Migration (PAFOM) and the new frequency of the PAFOM meeting to be held annually for senior officials and every two years for Ministers.’ Consequently, it was common ground that the terms of reference will come into force in 2022, notably following the 2020 forum in Senegal and 2021 in Rwanda.

Finally, the Executive Council validated the project to organise an extraordinary session of the CTS on migration, refugees and displaced persons in March or April 2020. The order of business of the session should comprise the following documents:

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* The draft statute of the African Humanitarian Agency before its submission to the extraordinary session of the STC on Justice and Legal Affairs and the 37th ordinary session of the Executive Council in June / July 2020.

- * The Draft Plan of Action on the Implementation of the Global Compact for Safe, Orderly and Regular Migration.
- * The draft Rules of Procedure of the STC on Migration, Refugees and IDPs prior to its submission to the STC Extraordinary Session on Justice and Legal Affairs and the 37th Ordinary Session of the Executive Council in June/July 2020.

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(B) Africa Report on Disaster Risk Reduction

Welcoming and endorsing the recommendations outlined in the report of the Specialized Technical Committee on Agriculture, Rural Development, Water and Environment (ARDWE), as contained in EX.CL/1187(XXXVI), and the First Biennial African Report on Disaster Risk Reduction (DRR), the Executive Council approved a series of frameworks and strategies aimed at consolidating the African Union's efforts in agriculture, rural development, water and environment.

The frameworks include:

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- * The Continental Framework to Boost Intra-African Trade in Agricultural Products and Services.
- * The AU Framework on Combating Antimicrobial Resistance, 2020-2025.
- * The AU Sanitary and Phytosanitary (SPS) Policy Framework.
- * The Strategic Framework for the Extension of the Holistic Country-led Model for Aflatoxin Control in Africa.
- * The Framework for Irrigation Development and Agricultural Water Management in Africa.
- * The African Union Framework for Sustainable Forest Management.
- * The Continental Framework to Boost Intra-African Trade in Agricultural Products and Services.
- * The Blueprint for Africa's Blue Economy Strategy.

As for the strategies, they include:

- * The AU Post-Harvest Loss Management Strategy and requests the Commission to identify institutions to be recognised as centres of excellence in post-harvest loss management.
- * The African Animal Welfare Strategy (AHSA).

Similarly, the Executive Council expressed its determination to promote environmental conservation in two statements:

* The Windhoek Declaration on Building Resilience to Drought and the Strategic Framework for Drought Risk Management in Africa.

* The Bobo-Dioulasso Declaration on reducing drudgery in agriculture for the benefit of rural women as part of the "confine the hand hoe to the museum" campaign and URGES Member States to accelerate agricultural mechanisation.

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